

European
Mining
in the Green
and Digital Era

Co-funded by
the European Union

22
Partners

8
Countries

13.84M
Total Budget

48
Months

The Project

MASTERMINE is the go-to ecosystem for mines that envision digitalisation, environmental sustainability, productivity monitoring and public acceptance within their strategic goals. It is based on an Industrial Metaverse approach to build a digitalized copy of a real-world mine.

CYBERMINE
Leading the digital transformation of mines

METAMINE
Introducing the “mining metaverse” of the EU mines

GEOMINE
Ensuring safety and stability in critical structures

AUTOMINE
Establishing autonomous and electric operations

4 EU demo cases

1 replication demo in South Africa

10 mines around Europe

10 different raw materials including 4 CRMs

GREENMINE
Enhancing the environmental sustainability of the mines

OURMINE
Fostering community engagement & social innovation

TERNA MAG MINES
Greece

TAPOJARVI MINES
Finland

Use Cases

The use cases include activities that cover the whole life cycle of the mine from exploration and mine design to closure and restoration and apply to the different stages of the extraction value chain.

THARSIS MINES
Spain

JSW MINES
Poland

SIBANYE-STILLWATER MINE
South Africa

Consortium

The MASTERMINE consortium consists of 22 partners from 7 EU member states (Spain, Greece, Finland, Germany, Poland, Italy, Cyprus) and one non-EU member (South Africa).

A strong, experienced, and interdisciplinary cluster that will contribute to the overall approach and achieve the objectives of the project.

SPAIN

GREECE

GERMANY

FINLAND

SOUTH AFRICA

POLAND

ITALY

CYPRUS

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